

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt-, Copper- and Palladium(II) using 1-(*o*-Carboxyphenyl)-3-benzoyl-5-phenylformazan

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A new, simple, rapid and accurate method for the spectrophotometric determination of divalent Co, Cu, and Pd using the title compound is described. The stoichiometric ratios of the formed complexes are 1 : 2, 1 : 1 and 1 : 1 (M : L) for Co, Cu and Pd respectively. The stability constants have been determined applying spectrophotometric methods. Beer's law is obeyed upto 4.71, 5.08 and 8.51 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-1}$ for Co, Cu and Pd respectively. The molar absorptivity, specific absorptivity, Sandell sensitivity and Ringbom range are presented. The effect of diverse ions has been investigated. A spectrophotometric titration method is suggested using EDTA and CDTA and the named formazan as reagent. The method has been applied successfully to the determination of Cu in alloy Samples.

The formazan skeleton is a good carrier of π -bonding and possesses chelating properties. The symmetry of the formazan molecule has been pointed out as a basic requirement for its good chelating and chromogenic properties¹. Copper was determined spectrophotometrically using 1,5-bis(2-hydroxy-4-nitrophenyl)-3-acetylformazan, 1,5-bis(2-hydroxy-5-sulphophenyl)-3-cyanofomazan, 5-(4-arsenophenylazo)-8-aminoquinoline and cupron². Cobalt was determined in micro-quantities using 1,5-bis(2-arsenophenyl) formazan and 1,3-bis(salicylidineamine)thiourea dihydrate³. A spectrophotometric method was developed for determination of divalent palladium using triphenylformazan, *p*-hydroxyphenylfluorone in the presence of emulsifier CTMAB, glyoxal bis(4-phenyl)-3-thiosemicarbazone and sodium pentamethylene dithiocarbamate⁴.

The present investigation deals with the use of 1-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-3-benzoyl-5-phenylformazan (1) for the spectrophotometric determination of bivalent Co, Cu and Pd ions.

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

The studies reveal that 50% ethanolic buffer solutions were the most suitable for developing the colour of the

complexes. The optimum pH values for developing the Co, Cu and Pd complexes are listed in Table 1. The maximum absorption of the complexes were used for further measurements. The effects of time, temperature, order of addition and solvents on the formation of these complexes were studied. The colour intensity for the Co complex increased slightly within the first 2 h and then remained stable for more than 24 h. In case of the Cu complex, the colour developed instantaneously and remained stable for more than 24 h. However, in case of the Pd complex the colour increased within 30 min then remained stable for about 4 h and then a slight decrease occurred. Raising the temperature up to 50° had no effect on the absorbance of the complex species. The addition of solvents such as methanol, acetone and dioxane up to 50% (v/v) had no effect.

TABLE 1—OPTIMUM CONDITIONS AND CUMULATIVE DATA FOR SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Co, Cu AND Pd

Parameter*	Co ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Pd ^{II}
Colour ^a	Greenish yellow	Orange	Orange
pH	6.1	4.1	4.0
λ_{max} , vs H ₂ O ^b	620	490	530
vs ligand	630	500	538
Beer's law range ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$)	0.00–4.71	0.00–5.08	0.00–8.51
Ringbom linear range ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$)	2.36–4.13	0.95–3.18	2.75–7.45
ϵ	5.19×10^3	1.42×10^4	9.70×10^3
<i>a</i>	0.008	0.223	0.092
<i>S</i>	0.011 4	0.004 5	0.010 9
<i>s</i>	0.001 6	0.004 4	0.004 7
<i>r</i>	0.999 9	0.999 9	0.999 7

* ϵ = Molar absorptivity $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, *a* = specific absorptivity ($\text{mg}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), *S* = Sandell sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$), *s* = standard deviation, *r* = correlation coefficient. ^aColour of free ligand is yellow. ^b λ_{max} of ligand = 440nm.

Nature and composition of the complexes : The stoichiometry of the complexes was studied using mole-ratio⁵, continuous variation⁶ and slope-ratio⁷ methods. The results indicate the formation of 1 : 1 (M : L) for the Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes and 1 : 2 (M : L) for the Co^{II} complex. The con-

ductometric titration curves for the Co and Cu complexes show breaks at molar ratio of 1 : 2 respectively, and 1 : 1 which is in accordance with the results obtained from spectrophotometric methods. The titration curves indicate a gradual increase in the conductance values due to the displacement of the protons from the ligand on complex formation⁸.

The overall formation constants (β_n) of the metal ions

TABLE 2—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE Co, Cu AND Pd COMPLEXES

Complex	Method*	M : L	log β_n
Co	MR	1 : 2	8.88
	CV	1 : 2	8.90
Cu	MR	1 : 1	5.07
	CV	1 : 1	5.09
Pd	MR	1 : 1	5.23
	CV	1 : 1	5.45

*MR = Mole-ratio; CV = continuous variation.

TABLE 3—INFLUENCE OF FOREIGN IONS ON THE ABSORPTION OF THE Co, Cu AND Pd COMPLEXES *

Ion	Co-I	Cu-I	Pd-I	Ion	Co-I	Cu-I	Pd-I
Na ⁺	-	-	-	Al ³⁺	+	-	-
K ⁺	-	-	-	Pb ²⁺	ppt.	ppt.	ppt.
Be ²⁺	+	ppt.	-	Vanadate	-	-	-
Mg ²⁺	+	-	-	Molybdate	+	-	+
Ca ²⁺	+	-	-	Tungstate	+	+	+
Sr ²⁺	ppt.	-	-	Cl ⁻	-	-	-
Ba ²⁺	ppt.	ppt.	-	F ⁻	-	-	-
Cr ³⁺	ppt.	-	-	Phosphate	-	-	-
Mn ²⁺	+	-	-	Acetate	-	-	-
Fe ²⁺	ppt.	ppt.	-	Oxalate	+	+	+
Fe ³⁺	+	-	-	Citrate	+	-	+
Co ²⁺	-	+	-	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	-	+	+
Ni ²⁺	+	-	-	Tartrate	+	-	+
Pd ²⁺	+	+	-	CN ⁻	+	+	+
Cu ²⁺	+	-	+	SCN ⁻	-	-	+
Zn ²⁺	+	-	-	EDTA	+	+	+
Cd ²⁺	+	-	-	CDTA	+	+	+
Hg ²⁺	-	-	-				

*(+) = Interferes; (-) = do not interfere; ppt. = forms precipitate; (x) = not used.

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN COPPER ALLOY SAMPLES

Sample	Composition (%)	Copper(%)		Std dev.
		Certified	Found	
Brass	Zn. 28; Pb. 0.006; Fe. 0.01	71.70	71.85	0.08
Brass	Zn. 32.26; Pb. 0.029; Fe. 0.002	67.28	66.93	0.203
Cu-Ni alloy (Berthier's alloy)	Ni. 32.00	68.00	67.12	0.227
Devard's alloy	Al. 45.00; Zn. 5.00	48.91	49.19	0.159

complexes were calculated using the spectrophotometric method⁹ and the results are presented in Table 2.

In case of the Co (47.14 $\mu\text{g}/10\text{cm}^3$), Cu(25.40 $\mu\text{g}/10\text{cm}^3$) and Pd (21.28 $\mu\text{g}/10\text{cm}^3$) complexes, up to 10-folds excess of the foreign ions were studied and the results are presented in Table 3. The results of Beer's law range, molar absorptivity (ϵ), specific absorptivity (a)¹⁰ and Sandell sensitivity (S)¹¹ are listed in Table 1. These values indicate that the methods are highly sensitive in comparison to the previously reported methods^{2,12}. Ringbom plot was drawn from which the Ringbom¹³ optimum range for analysis was determined and the values are listed in Table 1.

Spectrophotometric titration of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with EDTA or CDTA using I as indicator : The application of I as indicator for the spectrophotometric titration of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} ions with EDTA or CDTA was ascertained. It was found that upto 4.71 and 5.08 mg cm^{-3} of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively, can be determined with fair accuracy and precision using EDTA or CDTA.

Application : The method was applied for the determination of copper in brass, Cu-Ni alloy and Devarda's alloy. The results (Table 4) are in good agreement with the certified values.

Experimental

Benzoylacetone phenylhydrazone was prepared by the reaction of benzenediazonium chloride with benzoylacetone in molar ratio 1 : 1 in a slightly alkaline medium of sodium acetate¹⁴. The yellow product was kept in a refrigerator overnight, then filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 98° (lit. 98-99°).

1-(o-carboxyphenyl)-3-benzoylformazan (1): It was prepared by the reaction of diazotised anthranilic acid (0.01 mol) with the above benzoylacetone phenylhydrazone (0.01 mol) in aqueous NaOH¹⁴. The solution was then acidified with diluted 1 : 1 HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 177°. The results of elemental analysis of the formazan (1) were found satisfactory.

A 0.001 M solution of I was prepared in double-distilled ethanol. Solution (0.01 M) of CoCl₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O and PdCl₂ were prepared and standardised¹⁵. The buffers used were the modified Britton and Robinson universal series¹⁶. A Pye-Unicam SP 1750 spectrophotometer, a Lseibold G103 pH-meter fitted with a combined glass electrode, and an Elwro N5721 conductivity Cell were used.

Determination of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} : To solutions containing 2.36-4.13, 0.95-3.18 and 2.75-7.45 $\mu\text{g cm}^3$ of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} ions respectively, 1 cm^3 of 10⁻³ M solution of I in case of Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} and 2 cm^3 of 10⁻³ M of I in case of Co^{II} were added. The solutions were then diluted to 10 cm^3 with 50% ethanolic universal buffers of pH 6.1, 4.1 and 4.0 in case of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II}, respectively. The absorbances of the resulting solutions were measured at 630,

500 and 538 nm for the Co, Cu and Pd complexes respectively, against the reagent blank.

Titration of Co^{II} and Cu^{II}: Successive volumes of 10⁻³ M EDTA or CDTA were added to 10⁻³ M metal ion solutions (0.4–0.8 cm³) along with 2 and 1 cm³ of 10⁻³ M solution of I in case of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively. The solutions were made up to 10 cm³ with the recommended buffer solution. The absorbances were then measured at the recommended wavelengths.

Determination of Cu in alloys: The alloy samples were dissolved in least amount of a mixture of concentrated HCl and HNO₃, evaporated to dryness and diluted to 100 cm³. These solutions were used for the determination of Cu using the previously described procedures.

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